

ANALYSIS OF GLOBAL AND LOCAL SEISMICITY USING DATA FROM THE AIA SEISMIC STATION

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Continuous seismic monitoring at the Ukrainian Antarctic Station Akademik Vernadsky (AIA station, according to FDSN) has been carried out since 2000. A digital three-component seismic station Guralp-40TDE (Great Britain) with a frequency range of 30 seconds to 50 Hz is used for data collection. The station is equipped with a 24-bit digitizer and a Linux-based data acquisition module with a web interface. Time synchronization is performed using GPS.

The seismic region closest to the station is the seismically hazardous zone of the South Antilles Arc, which includes South Georgia, South Sandwich, South Shetland, and South Orkney Islands. A seismically active zone along the Bransfield Strait is also associated with rifting. During the instrumental observations, the nearest earthquakes were registered at a distance of up to 150 km from the station with an estimated intensity of up to 3-4 MSK. On average, several hundred seismic signals are recorded annually, the sources of which are earthquakes all over the Earth.

Along with teleseismic and regional events, a large number of high-frequency seismic signals of a local nature are recorded, due to the specific location of the Argentine Islands archipelago and the dynamics of the surrounding ice. The main sources of local seismic signals are cracking of the nearest glaciers of the archipelago, snowfalls and avalanches, and ice formation processes as a result of the descent of the Antarctic Peninsula glaciers closest to the station into the sea. Local sources also include icebergs hitting the seabed as a result of surf and seasonal changes in microseismic noise associated with sea ice.

Since 2022, the AIA seismic station has been connected to the network of seismometers on the Antarctic Peninsula, which has made it possible to automate the process of detecting seismic signals and receiving data in real-time to the National Data Center. The data is processed in the specialized software SeismicComp5. The AIA station's involvement in the real-time processing of seismic data allowed it to generate bulletins that are submitted to international seismological centers and available to the international scientific community.